

Development of NiTiO₃ Nanofibers by Sol-Gel Supported Electrospinning

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Nanofibers of transition metal oxides are familiar as intelligent materials for one dimensional nanostructure. In this study, we report that the NiTiO₃ nanofibers were prepared by sol-gel supported electrospinning method. These nanofibers were calcined at 450^oC to produce the NTO nanofibers. The SEM results revealed that the surface of the nanofibers are uniform and smooth, the fibers diameter got decreased after the calcination. The XRD analysis shows that the nanofibers possess rhombohedral structure. From the AFM images, it was confirmed that the as-prepared Nano Fibers have smooth surface, whereas the calcined Nano Fibers were not obtained because of the difficulty due to the roughness of the sample.

Keywords: Electrospinning, Nanofibres, Transition metal oxides.

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